

BBMRI Services Registration with Hostel step-by-step

1. <https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu> click on "sign in" at the top right.
2. Click on the button "with BBMRI-ERIC AAI...".
3. Click on "LifeScience Hostel".
4. Click on link in the lower left corner underneath the form field "Don't have account? sign up here!"
5. If necessary, perform the reCAPTCHA query "Please perform the confirmation below to continue" (check to confirm that you are not a robot and select the desired images).
6. Registration to the LifeScience Hostel: Enter the following:
 - a. - Name (first and last name)
 - b. - email
 - c. - Repeat e-mail
 - d. - Set a password (min. 8 characters, min. 1 letter and 1 number)
 - e. - Repeat password
 - f. - organization
7. Then click on "> Submit".
8. A page with "You have been successfully registered" will follow.
9. Search in your mailbox for a mail with the subject "LifeScience Hostel email validation" (also check the spam folder)
 - a. In the mail, the e-mail address is set as username.
 - b. Click on the link to validate your account.
10. A page will follow with the message "Your email address was verified".
11. Click on "Continue >" and wait until the redirection is complete.
12. Click on "LifeScience Hostel" again and log in with the specified email and password (see point 6).
13. Registration to the BBMRI:
 - a. Check the box "acceptable usage policy - i agree" and
 - b. click on the button "> Submit".
14. The following is a page with the message "You have been successfully registered".

It is now possible at any time to log in to <https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu> and <https://negotiator.bbmri-eric.eu> via "with BBMRI-ERIC AAI..." and "LifeScience Hostel" with the specified e-mail and password.

After login the "Consent about releasing personal information" has to be confirmed by clicking on "Yes, Continue".